

Research Article

Interactive Graphical Interface and Convergence Analysis of Taman Tasik Taiping: Utilising the Newton Backward Divided Difference Method for Educational Purpose

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Abstract: In this recent years, world are more depending on technologies. Therefore, in order to solve the mathematical problems, it is vital to implement the use of technology. This research is focuses on determining the perimeter of unsymmetrical objects by using the numerical analysis which is Newton Backward Divided Difference Interpolation method. Additionally, this research is to analyse the convergence of approximate perimeter which is to validate the method use to obtain the perimeter. Therefore, this work presents a MATLAB-based graphical user interface (GUI) for approximating and analyse the convergence of the perimeter of Taman Tasik Taiping with Newton Backward Divided difference interpolation method. Data was gathered by mapping the lake's map on graph paper and graphing coordinates, beginning with two points per region and then increasing to seven points. The GUI makes it easy to input and visualise data while computing the arc length for perimeter calculation. The results show that as the number of point increases, the approximate perimeter approaches the actual perimeter. This illustrates the applicability of numerical approaches and user-friendly tools for precise geographical perimeter analysis. As a result, this method prove the benefits of mathematical approach which can be benefit in real world problems. Hence, this method may be future potential for solving the perimeter with complex shape of objects or places.

Keywords: Convergence; Perimeter; GUI.

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1. INTRODUCTION

A perimeter is the measurement of the surrounding of an object. Dickson (1989) expresses area as a region's surface, whereas perimeter is the distance around it. In this study, it has been shown that the concept of perimeter is useful in many fields such as planning development, teaching process and among others. But in the present world there are so many techniques, even machines to measure the perimeter of the objects. For instance, coordinating for urban development, developing new

recreational parks, or any other related action may take time as well as be expensive. Therefore, this research was carried out to determine the perimeter of a certain area or object utilising the numerical analysis. Thus, it may improve the application of mathematics in today's setting.

According to Gautschi (2011), numerical analysis is a component of mathematics that provides tools and methods to solve numerical issues. Numerical analysis aims to develop or approximate effective solutions (Schatzman, 2002). Therefore, Newton Backward Divided Difference is the method used in this study to determine the perimeter. This approach is used to derive the interpolation equation, which may be applied to the arc length formula. These two methods play an important part in determining perimeter. According to Trifunov et al. (2021), interpolation is one of the most basic and useful numerical methods, and it is used to solve a variety of engineering issues. Aside from that, this study is helping to increase the world's appreciation for mathematics.

Consequently, Taman Tasik Taiping was chosen as the object of the study. This is carried out to make the study more practical and applicable to today's applications. Taman Tasik Taiping is one of the historical parks in Taiping, Perak. The approximate perimeter of Taman Tasik Taiping will be determined through numerical analysis in this study. Therefore, in the current study, the convergence analysis will also be adopted in order to compare the accuracy of the estimated perimeter with the actual perimeter through the Newton Backward Divided Difference approach.

Aside from that, this study incorporates modern advancements in technology. As a result, the Graphical User Interface (GUI) was used throughout this study to perform convergence analysis. There are numerous software options for creating the GUI, but this study was using MATLAB software, which allows it to create interfaces with User Interface (UI) components, as well as visual controls that represent common elements such as menus, buttons, lists, and windows, thereby improving program usability (Memon et al., 2003).

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This section explains all of the formulas and procedures used in this research. The methods employed in this study include numerical analysis to determine the perimeter as well as convergence analysis.

2.1 Data collection

Taman Tasik Taiping are the object chosen for this research. Hence, for the data collection, the reference photos are taken from the Google Map. Only a certain parts are taken for this research purpose. The actual and approximate perimeters are calculated to analyse the convergence analysis, therefore this study may compare both of these calculations, which is crucial for the convergence analysis. The reference photo taken from the Google map as shown in Figure 1.

Before obtaining both actual and approximate perimeter, the reference photo is drawn on the graph paper. Then, the drawn map on the graph paper are divided into four regions which labelled as A, B, C and D. The data collection for the approximate perimeter was gathered by plotting the coordinate points on each of the region.

Figure 1. Taman Tasik Taiping’s map (sources: Google Map).

2.2 Actual perimeter

The actual perimeter is measured by placing the thread on the sketched graph and measuring the length of the border using a ruler. This exactly depicts the actual perimeter of Taman Tasik Taiping. It may, however, be converted to real-world measurements in kilometers, as displayed on the Google Map.

2.3 Approximate perimeter

This study was using numerical analysis in order to determine the approximate perimeter of Taman Tasik Taiping. The method used is Newton Backward Divided Difference Interpolation and arc length formula.

To acquire an estimated perimeter, the coordinate points must first be obtained from the drawn graph paper. The Newton Backward Divided Difference Interpolation is therefore obtained by first creating a divided difference table. According to Komzsik (2007), Newton's approach provides a smooth approximating polynomial by passing over all input points. This study began with two plotted points in each region and increased to seven points per region. Table 1 below shows the divided difference table using two plotted coordinate points for one region:

Table 1. Divided Difference table.

x	$F(x_i)$	First Divided Difference
x_0	$f[x_0]$	$= f[x_0, x_1]$
		$= \frac{f[x_1] - f[x_0]}{x_1 - x_0}$
x_1	$f[x_1]$	

Then, using the information obtain in the Table 1 above, apply the Newton Backward Divided Difference Interpolation formula as shown in Equation 1 below:

$$P_n(x) = f[x_n] + f[x_{n-1}, x_n](x - x_n) + f[x_{n-2}, x_{n-1}, x_n](x - x_n)(x - x_{n-1}) + \dots + f[x_0, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n](x - x_n)(x - x_{n-1})(x - x_{n-2}) \dots (x - x_1) \tag{1}$$

This interpolation equation will then be put into the arc length formula. According to Zill and Wright (2009), integrals are commonly employed in engineering to calculate area, volume, and length. Hence, this study was employing the Arc Length in Cartesian Coordinates, as given in Equation 2 below:

$$\text{Arc length} = \int_a^b \sqrt{1 + [P'_n(x)]^2} dx \quad (2)$$

All of the steps above are repeated for the remaining three regions. The whole perimeter was then calculated by summing the lengths of all four arc lengths. Then, repeat the calculation to determine the perimeter of other number of plotted points in each region. This is to evaluate the convergence of the approximate perimeter towards the actual perimeter.

2.4 Error

Numerical computations might be incorrect caused by inaccuracies in the original data or in later processing (Hildebrand, 1987). This study utilised the relative error to evaluate the differences between actual and approximate perimeters by using difference number of plotted points in each region. By decreasing the error as increasing the number of plotted points use, it prove that the approximate perimeter is converges towards the actual perimeter. Below are the formula of the relative error used:

$$\text{Relative error} = \left| \frac{\text{actual perimeter} - \text{approximate perimeter}}{\text{actual perimeter}} \right| \quad (3)$$

In this study, the actual perimeter is by using the thread measurement meanwhile, the approximate perimeter is determine by numerical analysis. The steps from data collection until calculating the error need to be repeated using a different number of plotted points. To obtain each repetition, adding one point of coordinate in each region is necessary.

2.5 Convergence analysis

Limit of sequence is play an important role in this phase in order to analyse the convergence. To calculate the limit of sequence, firstly, determine the equation between the number of point used and the errors. From the six number of points and the errors, the equation can be derived by using the trendline features in the Microsoft Excel. Excel had features which function that allows users to fit six types of trend lines to data: linear, logarithmic, polynomial, power, exponential, and moving average (Hargreaves et al., 2010). Thus, by using exponential trendline, the line can fit the original curve of this study. Then, the equation can be used to calculate the limit of sequence as the number of points is approaches to infinity. The infinity represents that the number of coordinate points used are increases. However, to prove the convergence towards the actual perimeter, this study only calculated the full perimeter of Taman Tasik Taiping up to seven points in each region only.

2.6 Create the Graphical User Interface (GUI) using MATLAB

GUI was then created for this study to analyse the convergence easily. MATLAB software are used for this study for creating the multiple interfaces with difference function such as, calculating perimeter, errors and convergence analysis. By implementing the GUI, the visual representation are more interesting as it create the interaction between the computer and human and also GUI adapts the state of its widgets in response to user input such as mouse clicks, selections, and typing in textfields (Jansen, 1998). In addition, it also display graph and

the others component which helps users easier to analyse the convergence of the approximate perimeter.

3. IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Approximate perimeter

This section explain details the calculation of the perimeter of Taman Tasik Taiping by using three plotted points in each region. A 2-dimensional image of the sketched Taman Tasik Taiping on graph paper was recreated by using Microsoft Excel for the neat and clear visual. The image are shown as Figure 2 below:

Figure 2. A 2-Dimensional image of Taman Tasik Taiping's map on Microsoft Excel.

Figure 3. First region with three plotted points.

Figure 3 shows the three plotted points in the region A. Then, all the data were collected for the implementation of divided difference table. The divided difference table for three number of plotted points are shown as Table 2.

Table 2. Divided Difference table.

x	f(x)	First Divided Difference	Second divided difference
1.4	5.2	0.83333	-0.10802
5	8.2	0.05556	
8.6	8.4		

Then, from this divided difference, the interpolation equation can be obtain by using Newton Backward Divided Difference Interpolation formula as shown in Equation (1).

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_n(x) &= 8.4 + 0.05556(x - 8.6) - 0.10802(x - 8.6)(x - 5) \\
 &= 8.4 + 0.05556x - 0.47782 - 0.10802(x^2 - 13.6x + 43) \\
 &= 3.27732 + 1.52463x - 0.10802x^2
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4}$$

Next, the interpolation equation obtained in Equation (4) was then substituted into the arc length formula. The upper and lower boundary are taken from the initial and end of the x values in the region A.

$$\text{Arc length} = \int_{1.4}^{8.6} \sqrt{1 + [1.52463 - 0.21604x]^2} dx = 8.42172
 \tag{5}$$

Therefore, the arc length for region A by using three plotted points obtained is 8.42172. The same steps were repeated for the other three regions and the result was as shown in Table 3 below:

Table 3. Arc length for three plotted points.

Region	Arc length
A	8.42172
B	8.11842
C	10.03126
D	8.00615

Then, full perimeter of Taman Tasik Taiping using three plotted points was obtained by adding up all the arc length from each regions.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Total arc length} &= \text{Region A} + \text{Region B} + \text{Region C} + \text{Region D} \\
 &= 8.42172 + 8.11842 + 10.03126 + 8.00615 \\
 &= 34.57755
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{6}$$

The full perimeter obtain when using three plotted points is 34.57755 as shown in Equation (6). Then, the same steps from data collection until obtaining the approximate perimeter was repeated for the other number of plotted points in each region. Table 4 below shows the result of the approximate perimeter by using two until seven plotted points in each of the region.

Table 4. Approximate perimeter.

Number of plotted points	Approximate perimeter
2	31.3199
3	34.57755
4	34.62871
5	35.75300
6	36.16311
7	36.521

The table illustrates that the approximate perimeter is increase and converges towards the actual measurement for actual perimeter which is 38.3 by using thread.

3.2 Relative error

Relative error was then calculated by using the formula as shown in the Equation (3). The relative error for three plotted points in the region are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Relative error} &= \left| \frac{38.3-34.57755}{38.3} \right| \\ &= 0.09719 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Then repeat by using others approximate perimeter of difference plotted points in each region and the results are shown below:

Table 5. Relative error.

Number of plotted points	Error
2	0.1822
3	0.09719
4	0.09586
5	0.0665
6	0.05579
7	0.04645

Table 5 above indicates that the relative error are decreasing as the number of points use increase.

3.3 Convergence

Limit of sequence is used to evaluate the convergence analysis of the approximate perimeter. Thus the information of Table 5 was inserted into the Microsoft Excel and implement the equation by using the trend line feature. Then, the calculation limit of sequence are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} F(x) &= \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} 0.2547e^{-0.253x} \\
 &= (0.2547) \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} e^{-0.253x} \\
 &= 0.2547(0) \\
 &= 0
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{8}$$

The result obtain indicates that the error are getting zero as the number of plotted points are increase.

3.4 Graphical User Interface (GUI)

Figure 4. First interface.

Figure 5. Second Interface.

Figure 6. Third interface.

Figure 7. Fourth interface.

Figure 4 until Figure 7 shows the interfaces of this Peritech solver which creates using the GUI in MATLAB software, where it functions as the convergence analysis of the approximate perimeter. Figure 4 which is the first interface, display the functionality of each interfaces. Then, it also has the button start for users to click and the system will change the interface to the second interface. Figure 5 is for the user to calculate the arc length for each region and it requires users to reset in order to find the others arc length. Next, for Figure 6, it requires users to insert the number of points used and the perimeter obtain after sum up all the arc lengths obtain in the previous interface. Then, in this interface, it will display the graph of error and the number of points used. Then, after press the next button, the last interface will be display. Figure 7 will shows the result of the convergence analysis after the user enter the equation obtain in the third interface. All of this interfaces is using the User Interface (UI) component which creates the interaction between both computer and human. The components used as button, table and axes attract users to implementing GUI in their perimeter calculation, as this also helps users to obtain the perimeter easily.

4. FINDINGS

From the result obtained from limit calculation of sequence, it shows that the approximate perimeter is converge towards the actual perimeter. Figure 8 is the graph and the equation obtain from Microsoft Excel which display the error and its number of points used.

Figure 8. Graph and equation of error and number of points.

From Figure 8, y-axis represent as the error and the x-axis is number of points used in each of the region. The graph indicates that the error is decreasing and converges towards the zero value, as the number of points is increase. By using more plotted points in each region, it could enhance the convergence of the approximate perimeter towards the actual perimeter. However, this study only use until seven points to prove this result. Therefore, this shown that this numerical analysis method which is Newton Backward Divided Difference Interpolation method are useful in unveiling the perimeter of Taman Tasik Taiping.

5. DISCUSSION

This study has implemented the Graphical User Interface (GUI) which called Peritech, where it helps users in finding the perimeter of objects or places easily. GUI provides a user-friendly platform with the users where it involve the interaction between the computer and human. Peritech was created with multiple interfaces with difference function, but still it focuses to analyse the convergence between the approximate and the actual perimeter. Additionally, Peritech serve the interesting visual which displaying the axes. As a result, by using this Peritech solver for the calculation of Taman Tasik Taiping's perimeter, the result obtain was same as the manual calculation which converge towards the actual perimeter.

6. CONCLUSION

Perimeter of any objects or places can be identify by using numerical analysis which is Newton Backward Divided Difference method. This study has proved the applicable of numerical analysis in determining the perimeter in real application. Therefore, by implementing the GUI, this can develop a further studies and also could enhance the practical applications and be more appreciated towards the mathematics application in real life. In addition, for the further improvement, it is suggested to extend this study with other area and places with more complex geometric shapes. It is to validate the usefulness of this Newton Backward Divided Difference approach in more complexities real problem.

Acknowledgments: We have taken efforts in this project. However, it would not have been possible without the kind support and help of many individuals. I would like to extend my sincere thanks to all of them. We are highly indebted to all of my advisor, lecturers and teachers for their guidance and constant supervision as well as providing necessary information regarding the project and also for their support in completing the project. Their constant guidance and willingness to share their vast knowledge made me understand this project and its manifestations in great depths and helped me to complete the assigned tasks on time.

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